

SCHOOL LEADERS CAPACITY BUILDING FACTORS AND QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF RWANDA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7221744>

Published Date: 18-October-2022

Abstract: This study entitled, “School leaders capacity building factors and quality management in the public secondary schools of Rwanda” was guided by the general objective which is to determine the influence of school leader capacity building factors on quality management of secondary schools in the Rusizi District. In Rwanda, school leadership has generally been top-down, and as a result of these insufficient school management skills, school head teachers’ decision-making authority needed improvement in planning and greater autonomy in lesson preparation and evaluation. The research target population was 134 through which the sample size was drawn of 60 head teachers, 60 Deputy Head teachers, 12 SEIs, 1 DDE and 1 DEO. The results showed that there were factors of quality management which may lead to the school performance if the school leaders take them into consideration such as regular monitoring and evaluation, skills on school performance, capacity in decision making, planning for the education activities, and school leaders’ level of education. The research revealed that head teacher’s educational level contributes to effective quality school management as confirmed by 61% who responded strongly agree and 28% responded agree; for head teacher’s quality management planning as a key factor in school success, 57% responded strongly agree and 34% agree. The result showed that there was a strong positive relationship between the school leaders’ capacity building and quality management in secondary schools of Rusizi district as shown by the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation which was 0.7. The researcher recommended the Ministry of education through Rwanda Education Board to work closely with the districts to hire competent and skilled head and deputy heads of schools, the District of Rusizi should take its responsibility to provide regular trainings to the school leaders and deputy school leaders on how to manage the school resource effectively using available resources efficiently, then the school, Sector Authorities, General Assembly Committee and school community should work closely to ensure the school proper planning and conduct regular monitoring.

Keywords: School Leaders Capacity Building, Quality Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Globally, every nation's progress depends on education. As a result, governments all around the world, including the United States, have constructed critical intervention schools in a variety of nations, including some with high development and those that are still developing. The world will start key efforts aimed at improving education delivery and access for all individuals. The process of giving and acquiring education, on the other hand, is dependent on the administration of educational management at the national and school levels.

Continuous professional growth for school leaders is an experience that is both formal and informal that occurs all through the school leadership occupation (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012). Capacity building of school leaders is described as a result of increasing both school leaders' academic standing and their development of enhanced skill and efficiency in carrying out their professional tasks both inside and outside the school. That perspective appears to be appropriate for Rwanda. Both privileged and disadvantaged systems include processes, organizational mechanisms, and procedures designed to help school leaders improve and carry out their duties smoothly. Organizational processes and practices are means for managing school leaders' ongoing professional development. These could be short-term training courses and seminars that are designed and timed to satisfy the various professional needs of teachers and school administrators. Management techniques at a school, according to Holmes (2018), refer to how a headteacher manages human and other resources to maximize value and how the school interacts with the body that governs it. They can also refer to processes or tactics that are the most effective, practical, and efficient ways of reaching a goal while maximizing one's business and information (<http://www.businessdictionary.com>, 2014).

Leadership traditions and attitudes in schools are comparable to those in other institutions. Headteachers are regarded as critical to the efficient operation of many aspects of a school. According to Marvel and Morton (2016), the school administrator is the most important individual in terms of academic success, especially academic achievement performance, in the United States. He or she is in charge of all activities that occur within and outside the school. The tone of the school, the classroom atmosphere, the level of professionalism, student morale, and the amount of worry about what kids may or may not become are all set by the principal's capacity-building program. School leaders are the most important link between the community and the school, and how he or she performs in this job has a huge impact on parents' and students' attitudes toward the school. Andrews (2018) wrote about leadership, noting that effective school leaders are accountable for building a school-wide commitment to high standards and the achievement of all students. Principals of public high schools have been viewed as school managers for many years, and until two decades ago, strong standards were considered a prerequisite for academic achievement (Andrews, 2018).

According to Leith Hood's (2010) research, the school administration has a significant impact on student academic attainment. So, what leaders, instructors, and students do in schools and classrooms have an impact on student achievement. The drivers of capacity building in secondary schools include a lack of competent principals, teaching materials, school resources and facilities, principal leadership style, and student family background. Through this study, the training (capacity building) can also show their connection with the seen quality management of secondary schools in the Rusizi district, Rwanda.

1.2 Problem Statement

Different researchers agree that education is an important aspect of development (Marope, 2019; Bansal, 2020) in developing countries education is tied to the people's wellbeing and prosperity. In a country like Rwanda where education has had many changes and challenges, a lot has to be done to reach good quality education for all Rwandans. In this respect, a successful education system requires from all stakeholders a high level of accountability, but more importantly, it requires competent leaders who are ready to tackle all leadership and management challenges in education.

In its pursuit of good quality education, the Rwanda Education Board (REB) in collaboration with VVOB has started a capacity-building project known as Professional Standards for Effective School Leadership in Rwanda that aims at equipping school leaders with practical leadership skills with key competences required of them to fulfill their responsibilities and achieve school goals (REB/VVOB Rwanda, 2020). However there were still some Head teachers whose their schools were poorly managed due to lack of required skills and poor educational leadership and management. The effects of school leaders' capacity building on secondary school quality management in the Rusizi area will be explored in this case study. The study looks at how capacity development affects school leaders' managerial abilities as they strive to become more effective and dynamic leaders.

1.3 General objectives of the study

The overall goal of this research is to determine the influence of school leader capacity building factors on quality management of secondary schools in the Rusizi District.

1.4 Specific objectives

- (i) To evaluate the headteachers' capacity-building factors associated with quality management in the secondary school of Rusizi district.
- (ii) To explore the quality management of school requirements in public secondary schools of Rusizi district.
- (iii) To determine the relationship between headteachers' capacity building and quality management of Rusizi District's public secondary schools.

1.5 Significance of the study

In the process of school management skills, this research will be beneficial to students who need improving their learning through the application of quality management practices. Teachers in public secondary schools will benefit from the practices of quality management. The Ministry of Education of Rwanda will learn on how to improve the regular school leaders' capacity building for improving quality management skills. The school managers of the secondary school will learn how to implement their skills in managing their schools.

Secondly, the findings of this study will bring about the insight on school leaders awareness on the needed excises to boost the quality education via quality management.

Thirdly, findings of this study will give the data on how to improve their teaching and learning activities smart learning facilitate the users to improve their teaching and learning activities in secondary school of Rusizi district and Rwanda. Lastly, this research will facilitate the teachers and other educators on the awareness of the school resources management and monitoring and evaluation.

This study will evaluate the effect of school leader capacity building in improving effective Secondary school quality management in Rusizi District, Rwanda. The quality of School management and students' performance (academic achievement) is important to inform the policy intervention.

These research findings will be helpful to the parents, students, education leaders, and teachers on the strategies for sustaining the program in the outlying areas, especially in the villages in towns. The communities will gain information on how to maintain the program and employ it for the children for their performance and quality education. This will also provide education stakeholders with a deep understanding of impact of school leader capacity building on improving effective school leadership and administration in secondary schools in Rusizi District, Rwanda. This study will provide directions for further research, extension, and development of schemes that will benefit the scheme beneficiaries. Documentation of the identified problem will provide directions for the Ministry of Education, NGOs, and other national and international organizations whose foremost concern is efficient school leadership and management.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

The concept of school leader capacity building is discussed in this chapter, as well as school leadership and management functions, the impact of school leader capacity building on managerial functions, and theoretical and empirical research.

2.2 Head teachers' capacity building

Governments, voluntary organizations, non-governmental organizations, and individuals all contribute to the development and enhancement of school leadership professionalism. In theory, occupational training to become a headteacher does not finish with a teacher education college diploma. Many academics and practitioners, particularly in the field of education, are aware that aspiring school leaders begin their professional growth by enrolling in a teacher education and training program (Rodney, 2017). Even after graduation, the headmaster's professional development is a continual process (throughout his life). In short, Rwanda's policy concerning education and training stipulates that are mandatory to ensure the quality and professionalism of teachers (REB, 2016). Consequently, school leader professional development programs should be designed to keep school leaders in all roles to keep up with new professional, intellectual, educational, and societal issues (Moshu, 2016). Professional development programs are critical for school leaders because they help them to gain the essential abilities, particularly in the areas of school management and leadership.

2.3 The concept of organizational management capacity building

The concept of capacity building is described in most of the literature as spanning a wide range of issues. Kashu (2015). has sought to unpack the idea, stating that organizational managers might view capacity building as a means to development or as a goal in and of itself. As a result, it was critical to develop an analytical capacity framework to ensure that all education stakeholders had a shared understanding (Kashu, 2015).

Capacity building is a new concept which shows the characteristics of the effect of interaction. It arises from the flow of events that follow from situating a system in a certain context, which involves a complex combination of attitudes, resources, tactics, and capabilities. Capacity building entails the employment of many ways for its development, administration, assessment, and monitoring, as well as the provision of public value. Based on the above, it is difficult to reach an agreement on a definition of capacity building. The terms capacity development and capacity building are sometimes used interchangeably in the literature (Deborah, 2016).

2.4 Effective Quality Management

Understanding the Rwandan government's strategy of providing citizens with access to quality secondary education requires examining the capacity building of school leaders and its impact on quality management as a critical aspect in the successful execution of educational goals (Syarwani, 2012).

Therefore, this research aims to examine the capacity building and quality management of principals in public secondary schools in Rwanda. Education is one of the conditions for a country's long-term growth. It increases human resource quality and assures individual growth. However, when there is a shortage of high-quality secondary education, human resources are not appropriately used, and the country's socio-economic progress is hampered. Providing high-quality secondary education has become a pressing concern for most Rwandan families, contributing to other major issues such as unemployment and poverty. In Rwanda, quality education is determined by passing the standardized exam after each level. The National Examination Council administers the standardized national examination test for secondary education and different school inspections. The desire for equal treatment is a requirement that must be considered while working with the staff at all stages of the scientific chain. Rich companies, on the whole, have steady leadership. It should be promoted and nurtured as a source of strength for the company. Olorisade (2011) Effectiveness means the degree of goal attainment and the scope of the targeted problem-solving. It's a management aim that focuses on results, goals, and expected goals. It determines how well objectives in terms of quantity and time have been met. Syarwan has (2012).

The degree to which an organization accomplishes its aim is defined as effectiveness, and Olorisade (2011) defines organizational effectiveness as a result of both the quality and the organization's outputs, as well as the quality of the organization's processes and quality management in a school. In this case, is viewed as the school's ability to standardize educational inputs while producing high-quality graduates who are competitive in the market and employment, as well as pertinent to user requirements.

Quality management may be defined as a management technique standards; the nature of the treatment, performance, performance, or usage for a given purpose. This definition was used in this research. The National Examination and Schools Inspection Agency is in charge of developing policies, ensuring quality, establishing national standards, and supervising and evaluating education sector development programs.

2.5 Review of Empirical Literature

The head teachers' capacity-building factors in the secondary schools

The study conducted by Kazienamul (2017) on school leaders' leadership in urban secondary schools of Bangladesh looked at the relationship between school-based management and school improvement. The research seeks to define Bangladesh's school-based management system and investigates theories about the relationship between school leadership and school improvement, as well as the enabling of teacher development initiatives, which have an impact on this connection. Data was collected from 127 administrators and 697 teachers in a representative sample of 127 urban secondary schools in Bangladesh (n=127), with a total number of people of 338 and 10634 for principals and teachers, respectively. In this study, data analysis methods included multiple regression and hierarchical multiple regression. The study discovered that some of the major leadership characteristics in school-based management had a significant impact on school improvement and

teacher professional development. The results of the study produced useful information for politicians, education administrators, and particularly concerned school leaders and teachers with improving the secondary school well-being within the school-based administration system. While previous research has looked into the impact of various stories on school improvement, nothing has been done to look into the impact of the school principal's management abilities in a successful school administration. This research similarly collects data. Teachers' perspectives of the application of human skills in secondary school administration and how this affects their job satisfaction: A case study of Kenya's Baringo district (Bolei, 2012).

The quality management in the secondary school

Latif (2012) conducted a study on a model to teach pharmacy students in the US the managerial skills a constituent of management effectiveness. It went over the relevant management literature in terms of what proper management skills are and why they're necessary, as well as described an empirical research-based strategy for teaching management skills to pharmacy students. The premise was that the majority of pharmacists are managers because they have to be lead people and that fundamental managing ability can be transferred from one workplace to another. According to the research, pharmacy managers require conceptual skills (i.e. knowing how the many components of the firm interact with one another, a company, and the organization in general), Human, technical, and political skills to be effective.

It has also been found that mid-level managers' skills had very little effectiveness. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that there was no substantial association between middle-level administrators' management abilities and student academic achievement. According to the paper, a group of managers should employ their technical skills to improve classroom quality instruction by exposing students to conduct research in their chosen field of study; employ motivating skills to encourage academic personnel to research themes that will benefit their host communities and contribute value to the Nigerian society. This study and the present research had a good link; however, this study was centered on mid-level managers, whereas the current study focused on school leaders' management abilities. Once more, teacher training colleges were examined, while the focus of this research was on public secondary schools in the Rusizi district in Rwanda.

The relationship between capacity building and school quality management

Organizing, staffing, directing, planning, and regulating human and physical resources that are planned to support the fulfillment of organizational goals and academic success are identified as five managerial functions by Northouse (2017), as a managerial problem, planning is a dynamic procedure for determining today's judgments concerning future activities. It entails a variety of tasks to build a plan that coordinates people's efforts, and identifies, and deploys resources to meet certain objectives and goals. Mbiti (2017) contends that any strategy will be successful after commencing some methods to carry out the task and establishing a benchmark against which the goal-achieving process may be measured, with appropriate modifications made. Effective planning requires school leaders to be more disciplined and skilled in analyzing information and more insightful in dealing with uncertainty. Although planning has never been easy, in the future it will be due to the dramatically rising environmental complexity, increasing number of factors the quick obsolescence of even the most successful schemes, the rise in terms of the number of national and global events influencing businesses and the ever-shorter timeframes that may be planned with any degree of certainty are all factors to consider. Another management difficulty is an organization, which entails gathering the resources needed to meet the company's objectives and building the link between the activities of the organization and authority (Okumbe, 2017).

2.6 The Constructivism Management Theory

Among the most well-known school theories established to increase the efficacy of management in an organization is the bureaucratic theory of management. Jean Piaget was the father of constructivism theory in the years 1896-1980. Jean Piaget's appreciation of organizations stems from his observations of the modern western world's institutionalization of power and authority. According to Jean Piaget, the rules and a constructivism's rules exist to safeguard its constituents from supporting people develop their work. Rules and regulations, as well as unique tasks (labor division and specialization), are required. Bureaucracy also exists among secondary schools that are public and across the educational system. In today's world, when a school's personnel is multiracial, the headteacher must be well-versed in managerial abilities to apply the bureaucratic principle in his workplace. Flexibility is critical for good school management.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

The research conceptualizes these different variables within school leadership capacity building and effective quality management.

Source: Researcher (2022)

Figure 1

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design is primarily associated with investigating a phenomenon as it occurs (Creswell, 2013). The study will use a descriptive and correlative design to examine the effect of capacity building of school leaders on improving school quality management in the Rusizi district. Surveys are great for collecting raw data to study the factors that influence the occurrence of phenomena in a large population. This approach allows a vast population to be examined while only a small fraction of the population is required to contribute data. As a result, the researcher will be able to use this design to assess the effect of school capacity-building of leaders in improving the quality management of secondary schools in the Rusizi District.

3.2 Target Population

The study's target group includes 90 Headteachers from 90 public secondary schools in the Rusizi district, 90 deputy principals in charge of studies, 1 sector school inspector, 1 district school director (DDE), and 1 district education officer (DEO) responsible for secondary and vocational school.

3.3 Determination of sample size

Table 1: Sample size and target population

Population category	Total population	Percentage (%)	Sample Size
Head teachers	90	90%	60
Director of Studies	90	90%	60
SEI	18	100%	12
DDE	1	100%	1
DEO	1	100%	1
Total	200		134

Source: Rusizi district data, 2022

3.4 Sampling Technique

According to Rubin and Bellamy (2012), proportional sampling starts with dividing the population into relevant subgroups (strata). Therefore the approach of stratified simple random sampling is utilized and then a simple random sample from each stratum is used to obtain participants from that stratum. Therefore, in this study, the research will divide the participants into four layers (layer 1 principals, layer 2 deputy principals who will be in charge of studies, layer 3 SEI, and layer 4 will be district education officers). 60 principals and 60 DOS in 60 schools will be selected proportionally for participation in the study and 12 SEIs will be selected by census and DDE and DEO will be selected by the census, giving a total sample size of 134 participants.

3.5 Tools for Data Collection

Rubin and Babbie (2016) envisage that the research tools to be used should eliminate any subjectivity that the researcher might introduce. To obtain information from respondents, the following research tools are employed. The most common research tool is used to save sufficient time and ensure the quality of the information in the questionnaire. The researcher developed questionnaires for school leaders and DOS. Because the questions were open-ended and closed-ended, these tools were employed to capture data from both qualitative and quantitative sources. Open-ended questions do not provide respondents with pre-coded answers. Response categories were provided for closed-ended questions and respondents simply need to select one or more options. Using this method was required because open-ended questions aided respondents' decisions on closed-ended questions. In different sections, each study goal was addressed by the questions in the instruments. To gather comprehensive and relevant information, the researcher used the interview guide. This is used to collect data from the SEIs, DEO, and DDE. The instrument mainly contained open-ended questions. It is separated into sections where each subsection asks questions about specific study objectives. Interviews were conducted in person and over the phone. Both personal and telephone interviews were conducted. However, flexibility was a key consideration on the field response side.

3.6 Data Analysis Methods.

Data analysis, according to Alvi (2016), is the categorizing, data manipulation, and summarization to solve research questions. The Statistical Package for Social Scientists is used to code and analyze the questionnaire data (IBM/SPSS 21.0). This study's data will be analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Field data is gathered, cleaned, encoded, and recorded. To examine quantitative data acquired from headteachers and DOS surveys, descriptive statistics are applied. The percentages and frequency values are used to represent the results. For inferential statistics, regression and correlation analysis is used to evaluate for significance at a 95% confidence level. The qualitative data acquired through the interview guide is analyzed using content analysis. Thematic analysis of qualitative data is done by grouping them into related themes and counting similar replies based on the research objectives.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Data collection instruments returned

The research instruments were comprised of questionnaires distributed to the head teachers and Deputy Head teachers while the interview was conducted to the educational officials of the district of Rusizi. The researcher collected required data due to that all respondents were present during the study where 120 of 120 school head teachers and deputy director of studies equals to 100% returned the questionnaires and 14 of 14 equals to 100% educational officials of sector and district of Rusizi District provided information.

4.2 Presentation of the findings

Using the tables and figures, the researcher presented the study results and interpreted them in line with the three specific objectives which were: "To evaluate the head teachers' capacity-building factors associated with quality management in the secondary school of Rusizi district, to explore the quality management of school requirements in public secondary schools of Rusizi district, to determine the relationship between headteachers' capacity building and quality management of Rusizi District's public secondary schools". The researcher categorized the given information using frequencies and percentages.

4.3 The head teachers' capacity-building factors and quality management

The findings of this study were presented, interpreted regarding to the objectives where the first objective was to evaluate the headteachers' capacity-building factors associated with quality management in the secondary school of Rusizi district.

Table 2: The head teachers' capacity-building factors and quality management

Statements	SD		D		Neutral		A		SA	
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%
Enough training to improve my school academic performance	1	.8	7	5.8	1	.8	64	53	47	39
Attending continuous professional development for quality school management	4	3.3	9	7.5	2	1.6	47	39	58	48
Head teacher's educational level contributes to effective quality school management	6	5	4	3.3	4	3.3	33	28	73	61
Head teacher's quality management planning is a key factor in school success	3	2.5	7	5.8	1	.8	41	34	68	57
The head teacher's'/DOS human resource management skills to decision-making	8	6.6	11	9	3	2.5	36	30	62	51

Source: Primary data (2022).

The respondents were asked how the head teachers' capacity-building factors improve quality management in the secondary school of Rusizi district, and the results showed that 39% strongly agreed and 53% agreed that getting enough training improve school academic performance. As to whether school leaders attending continuous professional development for quality school management 48% strongly agreed and 39% agreed; they were asked if head teacher's educational level contributes to effective quality school management and 61% strongly agreed while 28% agreed; while asked if the Head teacher's quality management planning is a key factor in school success, 57% strongly agreed and 34% agreed; while asked if the head teacher's'/DOS human resource management skills enhances their better decision-making, 51% strongly agreed and 30% agreed. This implied that when school leaders are regularly well trained their quality school management skills enhance school performance in all school perspectives.

As stated by Kashu (2015). the organizational managers might view capacity building as a means to development or as a goal in and of itself. As a result, it was critical to develop an analytical capacity framework to ensure that all education stakeholders had a shared understanding (Kashu, 2015). There are several issues associated with the concept of capacity, Ownership, engagement, innovation, collaboration, learning, institutional development, decentralization, sustainability, participation, training, accountability, and performance improvement. The concept of organizational leader capacity building: empowerment and identity, and individuals acting together take some responsibility for their own lives in managing a school for excellence. Thus, as the other researcher stated, the capacity building entails the employment of many ways for its development, administration, assessment, and monitoring, as well as the provision of school competences. The terms capacity development and capacity building are sometimes used interchangeably in strengthening the school performances and competences (Deborah, 2016).

Interview analysis

"The use of managerial skills for leading a school help in effective school management and help in school performance, this helps the school to have good performance, to work in close with stake holders and the community, A good school leader must be well equipped in school management because under her/his responsibilities are human resource management, infrastructures' management, management of the students, management of the parents, different stakeholders in education and managing the school financially. Using managerial skills at school increases teachers and students motivation and concentration to reaching school mission as well as the school leader to achieve objective by using conceptual skills, good communication, technical and good decision making which allow all teacher to work in good condition with motivation of their leader. Another interviewee reported that using school managerial skills demonstrates boost of results. This means that

teachers and other staff are proactive and productive. There is also an improved communication, increase of commitment, morale among teachers, parents and students. Relationships are good, there is a good planning, there is knowledge management and critical thinking is created and promoted” (Deborah, 2016).

When recruiting the school leaders, the recruiters have to ensure the experience in teaching and learning, school leaders having skills in educational management, maturity, integrity, commitment, collaboration with others and having skills in decisions making.

Another one has responded the Head teachers who are prepared to use contemporary leadership approaches to improve teaching, learning and organizational performance. The recruiters have to establish an effective hiring committee that understand the specific leadership needs of school or district goals, recruit principal candidates based on the criteria that best meet school and district goals, identify strongest candidates and conduct an on-site performance assessment of finalists and plan for a smooth leadership transition.

4.4 Exploring the quality management requirements in public secondary schools

The results were demonstrated where the researcher used the frequencies and percentages.

Table 3: The quality management requirements in public secondary schools

Statements	SD		D		Neutral		A		SA	
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%
Maintaining quality management for determination of quality school management	6	8	11	4	2	14	64	42	37	32
Using adequate resources for quality management training	2	0	7	8	1	22	76	50	34	20
Implementing quality planning and assurance to improve quality management procedures	3	14	5	4	8	6	52	66	50	12
School monitoring is an effective requirement to school better performance in national examinations	9	4	2	10	1	2	74	48	34	36

Source: Primary data (2022).

The researcher was interested in exploring the quality management requirements in public secondary schools of the Rusizi district where the respondents were asked to demonstrate their level of agreements. As to whether the school leaders maintain the quality management for determination of quality school management 32% responded strongly agree; 42% responded agree. When asked if they use adequate resources for quality management training; 20% and 50% alternatively responded strongly agree and agree. When asked if they implement quality planning and assurance to improve quality management procedures; 12% responded strongly agree and 66% responded agree. While asked about school monitoring as an effective factor to school better performance in national examinations; 36% responded strongly agree while 48% responded agree. This implied that where quality management requirements in public secondary schools such as proper planning, adequate use of school resources, and monitoring and evaluation, the school performs effectively.

As a result, it was critical to develop an analytical capacity framework to ensure that all education requirements had a shared understanding (Kashu, 2015). There are several issues associated with the concept of capacity, ownership, engagement, innovation, collaboration, learning, institutional development, decentralization, sustainability, participation, training, accountability, and performance improvement. The concept of organizational leader capacity building: empowerment and identity, and individuals acting together take some responsibility for their own lives in managing a school for excellence.

Interview analysis

The researcher analyzed qualitative information collected using interviews from education officials including sector educational inspectors, District Education officer and Director of Education in Rusizi District on how a school poorly managed affects the school performance in terms of quality education and the informants responded:

When the school is poorly managed, affect both the school and students' performance. It is not easy for a school which is not well managed to perform well for different reasons which are: staff not motivated, stakeholders not involved, wide community not involved, SGAC does not work well, parents not involved.

Another respondent reported that the poor school management affect the school performance in many areas such as the school incompetent in all domains, results of students in National examination are mediocre, there is no punctuality at school both students and teachers even head teachers, indiscipline cases always appear at school on the side of teachers and on the side of students, there is no communication on the side of head teacher with teachers and parents, no collaboration between head teacher and teachers, parents and local community, the school is managed not as organization but it is in the hand of one person Head teacher, there is no planning for the school, teaching and learning are not lead.

4.5 The relationship between head teachers' capacity building and quality management requirements in public secondary schools

In this section, the researcher's task was to identify whether there was a relationship between head teachers' capacity building and quality management requirements in public secondary schools where the researcher set variables related to the head teacher's capacity building and how affecting the determination of quality policy in public secondary schools, head teacher's capacity building and how affecting quality planning and assurance in public secondary schools, and head teacher's capacity building and how affecting quality control and quality improvement in public secondary schools.

Using Karl Pearson coefficient correction, the results showed that was P-value was .01 which was significant, and strong positive correlation due to Karl Pearson Coefficient Correlation which was 0.7. This shows that when head teachers build capacity in planning for education activities, the school improves its quality management. When school head teachers are well trained and on quality control and school quality improvement, it improves the school quality management and increases the quality school leadership.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The researcher has concluded on quality management requirements such as proper planning, adequate use of school resources, and monitoring and evaluation, that they bring the school to the effectiveness of its performance. According to the respondents, once the school is not well managed there is no good school action plan, the budget is not well managed, the school personnel is not well organised, there is no vision, the school leader does not make regular follow up on school staff and learners' activities.

It was concluded that the relationship between head teachers' capacity building and quality management requirements among public secondary schools in the Rusizi district was strong positive correlation, which means that one the school leaders and deputy head teachers are well trained in all perspectives of quality school management, they create a school well equipped innovative competent and good vision.

5.2 Recommendations

The searcher has conducted this successfully through her determination and adequate information provided by the respondents. The data were analyzed, interpreted and discussed on how school leaders' capacity building influences the school quality management. After analyzing the data the researcher identified some the areas that need focus and provided the following recommendations:

The Ministry of education through Rwanda education Board should work closely to hire competent and skilled head and deputy heads of schools so that they provide quality education via quality management.

The District of Rusizi should take its responsibility to provide regular trainings to the school leaders and deputy school leaders on how to manage the schools effectively using available resources efficiently and assessing the impact they (regular training on school leadership) bring to the school performance.

The school, Sector Authorities, General Assembly Committee and school community should work closely to ensure the school proper planning and conduct regular monitoring for the purpose of maintaining effective teaching and learning activities.

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